

ANSWER TO CONSULTATION

TOPIC: Communication on achieving European Education Area
DATE: 25 August 2020
TO: European Commission
FROM: CESAER

CONTEXT

Recalling our positions [Vision for the European Education Area \(EEA\)](#), [Evaluation of the European University alliances pilot](#), [Sustainable funding for universities of the future in Europe](#), [Lead for research, education and innovation in recovery and to build resilience](#), we hereby emphasise four key messages that should be reflected in the 'Communication on achieving the European Education Area' as our answer on the [consultation for the communication](#).

In our view, to fully harness the potential and deliver on the objectives of the EEA, all future efforts must aim to:

ADOPT BOLDEST AMBITION

We encourage to adopt the boldest ambitions when shaping the EEA, thus i) establishing European knowledge societies as a community addressing specific values (such as equality, diversity and inclusion) and fundamental ones (such as democracy, rule of law, transparency and human rights) to safeguard academic freedom (to be promoted like freedom of speech and freedom of press) and institutional autonomy and support university leadership; and ii) enabling universities of science and technology to release unprecedented forces to contribute to ecological, economic and social sustainability and to act as autonomous agents of great transformation.

To fulfil its purpose, the EEA must be wide and open, not confined within the borders of the EU, but cover the signatory countries of the [European Cultural Convention](#) and provide for partnerships with neighbouring countries. We advise to establish Erasmus as the key EU instrument to implement the EEA along the example of the EU Framework Programmes for Research and Innovation for the European Research Area, and urge to focus Erasmus more on quality in line with [article 165 TFEU](#).

SECURE SUFFICIENT FUNDING FOR EDUCATION AND TRAINING AT ALL LEVELS

Advancing the EEA and turning it into reality will require sufficient and sustainable funding. Strategic investment in the future of our peoples through education and training will help to build a more modern, sustainable and resilient Europe. This should be realised by adopting an enforceable percentage of GDP target for funding for higher education in line with the best-performing regions in the world and including it into the European Semester. Moreover, synergies between different funding instruments, notably Erasmus and Horizon Europe, must be sought to effectively bridge research, education and innovation.

ENABLE STUDENTS, LEARNERS AND TEACHERS TO CONTRIBUTE TO A SUSTAINABLE FUTURE

The priorities of the EEA must shift from ensuring the employability of students and learners to (i) equipping students, learners and teachers with the knowledge, skills and competences

necessary to tackle the grand global challenges; (ii) enabling them to meet the demands of changing European knowledge societies; and (iii) empowering them to contribute to ecological, social and economic sustainability. To achieve this, new instruments to facilitate lifelong learning and ensure the continuous access to reskilling and up-skilling at any stage of life must be developed. They should include micro-credentials, help address the shortage of STEM graduates, as well as ensure better entrepreneurial knowledge and skills.

ENSURE MUTUAL RECOGNITION OF QUALIFICATIONS AND LEARNING OUTCOMES FROM ABROAD

Although considerable progress has been made, the mutual recognition of qualifications and learning outcomes abroad remains a lingering problem for students and universities across Europe and beyond. Instead of relying heavily on European Universities as a promising cure-all, efforts should continue in parallel (i) to implement a [European Student Card](#) allowing automatic recognition of [ECTS](#) credits for the open and wide EEA, and not only the EU; (ii) to improve the application and working of the [Lisbon Recognition Convention](#); and (iii) to collect and share experiences and best practices.

We offer to continue pro-actively and constructively contribute to shaping and implementing the EEA by 2025.

For more information and enquiries, please contact our Advisor for Higher Education [Indrė Antanavičiūtė](#).

[CESAER](#) is the European association of leading specialised and comprehensive universities of science and technology that: champion excellence in higher education, training, research and innovation; influence debate; contribute to the realisation of open knowledge societies; and, deliver significant scientific, social, economic, and societal impact.

Please reference this document using <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3999499>